

Deliverable D2.1

Project Data Management Plan

Project Title (Grant agreement number)	EOSC-ENTRUST Grant Agreement 101131056		
Project Acronym (EC call)	EOSC-ENTRUST		
WP No & Title	WP2 Project Data Management Plan		
WP Leaders	Peter Maccallum (ELIXIR Hub)		
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary	1. ELIXIR Hub		
Contractual delivery date	30/11/2025	Actual delivery date	28/11/2025
Delayed	No		
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable	ELIXIR Hub		
Authors	Maria Tyler (ELIXIR Hub) Mado Fernandez (ELIXIR Hub)		
Contributors			
Acknowledgements (not grant participants)			
Reviewers	Martina Caloi (ELIXIR Hub)		

Log of changes

Date	Mvm	Who	Description
28/10/2025	0v1	Mado Fernandez (ELIXIR Hub)	Initial version
13/11/2025	0v3	Mado Fernandez (ELIXIR Hub)	Version ready for Management Board review

25/11/2025	0v5	Mado Fernandez (ELIXIR Hub)	Version ready for submission
------------	-----	--------------------------------	---------------------------------

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This deliverable is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

Table of contents

1. Executive Summary	3
2. Contribution towards project objectives	5
3. Introduction	7
4. Description of work accomplished	8
4.1 EOSC-ENTRUST Project Repository	8
4.1.1 Introduction and background	8
4.1.2 Project Repository Structure	10
4.1.3 Access	11
4.1.4 Registration (mailing list and repository access)	11
4.1.5 Data protection	11
4.2 Open Science Practices	12
5. Results	13
6. Conclusions	13
7. Impact	13
8. Next steps	13
9. Deviation from Description of Action	13
10. Annexes	14
10.1 EOSC-ENTRUST project participants registration form	14
10.2 EOSC-ENTRUST Kick-off registration form	18

1. Executive Summary

The Data Management Plan (hereinafter “the project DMP”) is a mandatory deliverable by the European Commission (EC) that is tailored to the specific project activities and documents the relevant project repositories and how they are managed. The DMP for EOSC-ENTRUST is developed by WP1 as an integral part of the governance structure, and also oversees the quality assurance of the project outcomes. The project DMP considers exemplars of the relevant forms used across the project to gather personal data.

The project DMP is a live document that will be reviewed and updated periodically to ensure it remains relevant throughout the lifetime of the project. The deliverable has been revisited at month 21.

2. Contribution towards project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'.]

	Key Result No and description	Contributed
Objective 1 Create a European network of Trusted Research Environments, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.	1. A catalogue of suitable national or institutional TREs as part of the EOSC offering (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15)	Yes
	2. A 'starter pack' of exemplar projects to demonstrate how networks of TREs can address European research priorities (WP4/5/6, WP7/8/9)	Yes
	3. European researchers are aware of capabilities through communication and outreach events (WP4/5/6) and materials delivered to support national TRE training programmes (WP4/5/6, WP13/14/15)	Yes
	4. Enable federated use via standards and technology for trusted researcher identity, data use and data access linked to developing European framework for trusted electronic identification of individuals (WP16/17/18)	Yes
	5. Enable researchers and software developers to deploy across multiple TREs via secure FAIR digital objects and workflows (WP16/17/18)	Yes
	6. EuroHPC capacity that meets the need for secure exascale and GPU (e.g., AI) computing can be identified and connected using the EOSC-ENTRUST framework (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).	Yes
Objective 2 Trusted Research Environment providers implement,	1. An established European network of national and institutional TRE Providers (WP10/11/12)	Yes
	2. A service blueprint that allows technical interoperability between TRE based on the EOSC Interoperability framework (WP13/14/15)	Yes

<p>validate, and promote their capabilities through a European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language.</p>	<p>3. National and institutional TREs consistently set out their capabilities with common representation for validated legal, operational, semantics and technical aspects (WP10/11/12).</p> <p>4. Define the security baseline and auditing procedures for TREs to support the Five Safes¹ principles and capture requirements in guidelines for FAIR sensitive data in EOSC (WP13/14/15)</p> <p>5. Drive TRE composability via policy and process interoperability and set out an EOSC compliant governance model for a TRE services network (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).</p>	<p>Yes</p> <p>Yes</p> <p>Yes</p>
<p>Objective 3</p> <p>National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes</p>	<p>1. A machine-readable catalogue of TRE capabilities allowing detailed, comparative analysis of technical capabilities and identification of gaps (WP10/11/12, WP13/14/15).</p> <p>2. Policy briefs on the capabilities of the European TRE Provider Forum (WP4/5/6, WP10/11/12) and Use Cases of their application in research domains of high societal impact (WP7/8/9).</p> <p>3. Connection between the EOSC-ENTRUST Provider Forum and the European Data Spaces (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>Yes</p> <p>Yes</p> <p>Yes</p>
<p>Objective 4</p> <p>The European Network of Trusted</p>	<p>1. National and organisational providers are incorporated into EOSC via national members and the European network forms part of EOSC long-term strategy (WP1/2/3, WP4/5/6).</p>	<p>Yes</p>

¹ Ritchie, F. (2017, September). The "Five Safes": A framework for planning, designing and evaluating data access solutions. Paper presented at Data for Policy 2017, London, UK

Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the European Open Science Cloud and the European Data Spaces and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.	2. The emerging European Data Spaces build their capabilities on the network of existing and developing TRE providers (WP4/5/6).	Yes
	3. Technological developments required by one Data Space activity can be directed to a forum of TRE specialists, reducing the need for duplication and coordinating investment in foundational technologies (WP10/11/12).	Yes
	4. A driver project to demonstrate opportunities for public-private partnerships (WP7/8/9)	Yes

3. Introduction

The purpose of EOSC-ENTRUST is to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments for sensitive data and to drive European interoperability by joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis. As the main outputs of this project will be best practice resources, requirements documentations, architecture, specifications, validation reports and workflows, it is not expected that research data will be generated and maintained.

EOSC-ENTRUST brings together providers of operational Trusted Research Environments from 15 European countries with a shared goal to implement, validate and promote their capabilities through a common European framework using shared standards and common legal, operational and technical language.

EOSC-ENTRUST has identified four driver projects (use-cases) covering Genomics, Clinical trials, Social science, and public-private partnerships to benchmark capabilities, inform blueprint design and demonstrate secure data analysis using federated workflows. The Driver projects are based on existing, on-going studies with approval for data analysis in place. The use of personal data in the driver projects will not be for additional analysis and will not be shared between beneficiaries.

In this deliverable (the Project Data Management Plan) we provide an overview of the project data repository, including how personal data is processed for the purpose of project coordination and management and address the Open Science Practices.

- EOSC-ENTRUST Project Repository ([section 4.1](#)) including:
 - Overview of the project data repository
 - Access level
 - Registration and consent procedures.
- Open Science Practices ([Section 4.2](#)) including:
 - Open Access to publications

The deliverable has been drafted by the ELIXIR Project Management Office and reviewed by the ELIXIR Legal Services.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 EOSC-ENTRUST Project Repository

4.1.1 Introduction and background

ELIXIR makes use of the legal personality of an intergovernmental organisation, i.e. the European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL), based on the international treaty “Agreement Establishing the EMBL” <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/governance/faqs> . ELIXIR also makes use of some of EMBL’s infrastructure and administrative services, provided by EMBL as the host, to the ELIXIR Hub. More general information about EMBL’s legal status can be found here: <https://www.embl.org/administration/legal-services/>

Among the services provided by EMBL as ELIXIR’s host, ELIXIR uses the EMBL-EBI data repositories to store and share project-related data with project participants. These repositories do not store research data, but administrative project data required to manage, monitor and control the project execution. ELIXIR also intends to use one of these repositories in relation to EOSC-ENTRUST (hereinafter ELIXIR repository) to monitor and control EOSC-ENTRUST project administrative, legal, financial and technical aspects providing a collaborative workspace to generate project deliverables, milestones and manage internal and external communication activities. At the same time, it aims to foster collaboration across project participants.

A Google Shared Drive (hosted in the EU) is used as the project repository. Access to the repository is granted, by the Shared Drive manager, i.e. the Project Manager, only once the participants have been registered and verified, see section 10.1 Project Participants registration form.

4.1.2 Project Repository Structure

Top Level Folders	Content
Project Master Files	<p>Master file with details from the project: contact lists, effort distribution, lists of deliverables & milestones, GANTT chart etc</p> <p>Project monitoring spreadsheet: contains details of all actions, events, risk monitoring, deliverables and milestones, along with due dates and templates - monthly reports are generated from this for all partners/WPs.</p> <p>Communication registration form responses: It includes the email address of the partners' participants that are relevant for the monitoring and control activities: PIs, Deputies, administrative, financial and legal contacts.</p>
Legal Documents	Legal documents pertaining to the project: Consortium Agreement, Grant Agreement, Description of Action, amendments, contracts, etc.
WPs	Working folders for the WPs.
Deliverables & Milestones	Repository for project deliverables and milestones (templates, working drafts and submitted documents).
Project meetings, events & TCs	Details of all project meetings and events (agendas, minutes slide presentations etc).
Periodic reporting	Financial and periodic reports from all project partners
Guidance and templates	<p>Project handbook, containing guidance pertaining to all aspects of the project (processes, communications, management structure and responsibilities, etc).</p> <p>Project templates: deliverables, milestones, agendas, minutes, slide presentations, etc.</p>
Project Communications and Outreach Materials	Project branding & style guidelines, press releases, articles, presentations, newsletters, etc.

4.1.3 Access

All project participants that have registered obtain edit access to the EMBL-EBI-hosted project repository managed by the ELIXIR Project Management Office Team.

4.1.4 Registration (mailing list and repository access)

The registration form is available in [Section 10.1](#).

4.1.5 Data protection

4.1.5.1 Data protection officer

As indicated under 4.1.1 ELIXIR uses EMBL's legal personality. EMBL is a distributed intergovernmental organisation and as such benefits from privileges and immunities, such as exemptions from the applicability of national law, in order to allow for the efficient exercise of EMBL's official functions and to create a uniform legal environment within EMBL across all sites. In the context of data protection, this means that EMBL is not subject to GDPR, which does not apply to international organisations. However, EMBL is still subject to internal data protection rules which reflect the principles and approaches of European data protection law. More information about data protection can be found here <https://www.embl.org/info/data-protection/>.

The Data Protection Officer's details are provided in the [ELIXIR privacy statement](#) and copied below:

EMBL Data Protection Office

Email: dpo@embl.org

EMBL Heidelberg, Meyerhofstraße 1, DE 69117 Heidelberg, Germany

4.1.5.2 Personal Data Collection Management and oversight process

The project will be collecting personal data from project participants in the following scenarios:

- During the registration as project participant - required to get access to the project repository.
 - Personal data collected: full name, institutional email address and telephone number, personal email (if needed for access to the repository), country (of employer institution), project role.
- When registering to attend face to face and virtual meetings: Project meetings (e.g. General Assembly), training events or workshops.
 - Personal data collected: full name, institute affiliation, gender, dietary requirements, accessibility requirements.

The minimum set of information required for running the events is and will be collected. Data collected is kept on the ELIXIR repositories for the period of time requested by the EC in order to allow access to registries in case data needs to be audited.

4.1.5.3 Personal Data Collected

Details of data being collected in the different scenarios (e.g. registration as project participants and meeting registration) can be found in [Section 10](#).

4.1.5.4 Personal Data Transferred from EU to a non-EU country or international organisation

During the project, should personal data be transferred from the EU to a non-EU country or international organisation, confirmation that such transfers are in accordance with Chapter V of the General Data Protection Regulation will be included in a following iteration of the DMP.

As indicated under 4.1.1 ELIXIR is subject to EMBL's data protection scheme.

Transfers of participants' personal data to ELIXIR are done in compliance with chapter V of the General Data Protection regulation.

4.1.5.5 Personal Data Transferred from non-EU country to the EU

No transfer of personal data collected in a non-EU country to an EU country (or another third state) is foreseen in the project activities. Should such a transfer take place during the project, confirmation that such transfers comply with the laws of the country in which the data was collected will be included in a following iteration of the DMP.

4.1.5.6 Informed consent procedures

Special categories of data (i.e. dietary and accessibility requirements) processed for the overall organisation and participation management of project-related events are processed based on the project participants' consent. The form used to collect consent for processing of special categories of data is included in [Section 10.2](#).

4.1.5.7 Further processing of previously collected personal data

No further processing of previously collected personal data is envisioned in this project. Personal data has been collected using the participant registration form (see section 10).

4.1.5.8 Evaluation the ethics risks related to the data processing activities of the project

The personal data collected is limited to that necessary for the management, monitoring and control of the awarded project.

Considering that the project only processes data of project participants for administrative purposes, no additional risk assessment has been identified as required at the time of producing this deliverable.

4.2 Open Science Practices

As per the Grant Agreement Part B Art 1.2.10 Open Science Practices the EOSC-ENTRUST project will comply with the EC's open science obligations set out by Horizon Europe².

² EC Open Science Policy

https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

5. Results

ELIXIR repositories used to store EOSC-ENTRUST Project related data, including personal data are described in this document.

6. Conclusions

At the time of submission, this deliverable addressed the description of the project repository and how this is managed. The document will be updated as indicated in [Section 8](#).

7. Impact

This deliverable provides the basis to collect and manage the personal data indispensable for the project execution.

8. Next steps

This deliverable will be re-visited in case of modifications on the Grant Agreement and at month 21 of the project.

9. Deviation from Description of Action

Deliverable submitted on time and after conducting the project quality assurance processes defined in D1.1 Project Handbook.

10. Annexes

10.1 EOSC-ENTRUST project participants registration form

Registration of Participation in EOSC-ENTRUST (EC HE 101131056)

The data you enter below will be used for the dissemination of information pertaining to the grant preparation and execution of the Horizon Europe EOSC-ENTRUST project (Grant number: EC HE 101131056).

Before filling in the form, please read our privacy statement [here](#).

mado@ebi.ac.uk [Switch accounts](#)

 Not shared

[Next](#) [Clear form](#)

Registration of Participation in EOOSC-ENTRUST (EC HE 101131056)

mado@ebi.ac.uk [Switch accounts](#)

Not shared

* Indicates required question

Participant Contact Details

The information provided below will be kept in a Google Sheet within the project folder so we can add you to our collaborative project repository, to the relevant distribution lists and to send physical documentation if required (e.g. certification of attendance at meetings). In case you can't provide some of the information requested at this point, or prefer not to, we will endeavour to explore other ways to ensure you can still engage and contribute to the project. Please contact us at grants@elixir-europe.org.

Name *

Your answer _____

Surname *

Your answer _____

Select your Organisation/Institution (among the ones taking part in EOOSC-ENTRUST). *

- ELIXIR Hub
- EMBL-EBI
- CSC
- BSC
- EUDAT
- HEALTH-RI
- MU
- SIGMA2
- UiB
- NTNU
- UiO
- SURF

- DeIC
- BIP4DAB
- TURKU
- UTARTU
- PNED
- UL
- ECRIN
- IT4I@VSB
- VIB
- Sciensano
- CESSDA
- TARKI
- GESIS
- THL
- CRG
- GRNET
- UNIBI
- UU
- HDR-UK
- UNIMAN
- UNIVDUN
- UNOTT
- UESSEX
- Other: _____

Position

Your answer _____

Organisation/Institution address. Note: This information (along with city, country and postcode details) will only be used if we need to send you original documents, e.g. certificate of attendance. If not provided now we will need to request it at a later stage.

Your answer _____

Organisation/Institution Post Code

Your answer _____

City

Your answer _____

Country

Your answer _____

Please provide us with your institutional contact details (email). Please do not provide personal contact details (e.g. gmail addresses). *

Your answer _____

If your institutional email address does not allow you to access Google Drive, please provide an alternative gmail address / email address that allows access (sharing of project documents will be done within GDrive). Please contact us at grants@elixir-europe.org if access to GDrive will be a problem.

Your answer _____

Organisation/Institution Telephone number (for urgent communication - e.g. meeting/travel updates).

Your answer _____

Social media profiles and hashtags, if provided (optional) will be used to support the project communication and outreach activities

Your answer _____

Where do you primarily consume news related to work? E.g. social media or any other news platform. If provided (optional) will be used to design project communications campaigns

Your answer _____

[Back](#) [Next](#) [Clear form](#)

10.2 EOSC-ENTRUST Kick-off registration form

 eosc | **ENTRUST**
European Network of Trusted Research Environments

Summary ▼

! The registration process is still closed for your attendees but you have enough rights to test it

Open process

Profile information

 ^

Email

First name *

Last name *

Event registration details

 ^

I'm a

Prior to entering your details for registration, please read the [ELIXIR Events Privacy Statement](#) which includes information regarding the personal data you provide, the processors we use to deliver events and how you may exercise your rights over your personal data submitted to ELIXIR.

Institute / Organisation *

If you have indicated 'Other', please add the name of your institution here

Please indicate which WP or Board you represent *

- WP1ABC - Project Coordination and Strategic Alignment
- WP2ABC - Communication, Dissemination & Outreach
- WP3ABC - Drivers: Validating blueprints across Governance domains
- WP4ABC - TRE Provider Forum
- WP5ABC - Trusted research environment blueprint
- WP6ABC - Trusted researcher identities and data authorisation
- WP7ABC - RO-Crate and workflow processing
- Administration and Finance
- Legal representatives
- PIs and Deputy PIs
- Scientific, Ethics and Industry Advisory Board

Gender *

Will you be attending in person or virtually? *

- In person
- Virtually

Dietary and special requirements

Your dietary and other special requirements are processed based on your consent according to the [ELIXIR Event Privacy Statement](#).

You are not obliged to provide any such data to us. However, without it, the ELIXIR Events team will not be able to facilitate your taking part in ELIXIR events by accommodating your dietary or other special needs. Specifically, please be aware that if you have any food allergies but you do not consent to processing of personal data with regards to dietary requirements, the ELIXIR Events team will not be able to ensure that catering at the event offers allergy-safe options.

I consent to the processing of data on my special requirements *

Yes

No

Digital content at ELIXIR events

Occasionally, the ELIXIR Hub may record videos and/or take photographs to promote the event. By attending the event you consent to be video-recorded and/or photographed. You also consent to the further use of the video-recordings and photographs for promotional purposes, i.e. publication of this material on ELIXIR webpages (e.g. ELIXIR public website and intranet) and ELIXIR social media accounts. You may withdraw your consent at any time by emailing us at dataprotection@elixir-europe.org or by informing the event organisers at the reception desk on the day of the event. For further information on data protection and your respective rights, please consult with the [ELIXIR Events Privacy Statement](#).

I do not wish to be video-recorded and/or photographed

I understand that it is my responsibility to make myself known to the event organisers at the reception desk.

The [ELIXIR Code of Conduct](#) has been created to ensure that people at ELIXIR events can interact with each other in a respectful and safe environment. It provides ways you can voice your concern if you believe there has been a breach to this Code of Conduct. The ELIXIR Code of Conduct will be in place at this event.

Next

[Back to the event](#)